

Development of Logical Thinking of the Teacher as a Pedagogical Problem

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Abstract:

The modern education system requires teachers to have not only knowledge and skills, but also the ability to effectively solve problems in the educational process. This shows that logical thinking is very important in the teacher's professional activity.

Logical thinking is a tool that allows you to analyze problems, find solutions and implement decision-making processes. Therefore, the development of logical thinking is the basis of the professional success of any teacher.

This article talks about the possibilities of the teacher to use logical thinking in the educational process, the problems encountered in this process and ways to overcome them, as well as the modern methods of developing the logical thinking of the teacher.

Keywords: Logical thought, creative thought, intellectual potential, pedagogical skills.

Today, the training of highly qualified pedagogues capable of logical thinking has become an urgent issue in the field of education. To reach an improved point of logical thinking in the conditions of managing the lessons of elementary school students of an educational institution for future specialists, it is, on the one hand, the basis of the logical development of a choice or solution, its implementation, on the other hand, educational and educational all components of the process, teachers, students, parents' interests, and the support of self-governing bodies help to increase the positive coefficient.

The process of logical individualization of a teacher in pedagogical work can have the following different expressions:

- individual differences as a partial or episodic manifestation of dissimilarity in professional behavior and activity;

- individual method that is kept stable for a long time in professional activity, individual generalization of methods and tasks of professional activity;
- individuality, individual professional worldview, often an individual variant of the professional type in the work of a teacher

Logical thinking, on the one hand, individualism, on the other hand, is considered the basis of reality and creative individuality, an effective form of self-awareness, and it also implies the following psychological characteristics:

- realizing the uniqueness of a person when comparing himself to others;
- creative expression and manifestation of ideas about oneself;
- integrity and harmony of individual intellectual (unit of logical thinking), internal unity;
- the true nature, logic, dynamism and continuity of the process of self-development of a person, his formation as a creator;
- self-emphasis of a person and awareness of his competence;
- self-realization of the creator and realization of his importance in personal and social aspects.

Thus, the structure of the teacher's innovative activity consists of functional components, criteria, level and structural components.

Therefore, in the development of logical thinking competence of future pedagogues, it is necessary to take into account modern requirements for textbooks and training manuals, to make extensive use of scientific and technical achievements, and their creative qualities. The pedagogic character of the directed assignments cannot be denied. Thus, the analysis of scientific, scientific-methodological literature revealed that the need to evaluate the concept of "logical thinking" in the context of modernity was scientifically proven as a social need. During the observations, it is assumed that the state of methodical preparation of future pedagogues for improving logical thinking skills has the following character and can be further developed and improved based on some basic criteria:

- to be able to identify the main and essentially primary ideas in the perception of the educational material in the lessons given to the future primary school teachers;
- imparting fundamental knowledge of teaching analysis, synthesis, analogy, prediction;
- developing students' thirst for knowledge, preparation for independent life;
- Developing the intellectual level of their personality and forming a culture of debate.

Under the influence of changes in the democratic and innovative mood in the educational sphere, future elementary education teachers prefer freedom of choice, independent creativity and research opportunities in solving problems of their logical worldview and professional development.

Also, the current scientific conditions and state of the research problem require to dwell on the essence of pedagogical modeling from the point of view of developing a model and software for the development of professional-intellectual competence in future pedagogues in the context of logical approaches and interactive methodical technologies. According to the nature of the researches related to this issue and carried out in this field, mainly person-oriented approaches, dual education, classification of pedagogical technologies, integrative, creative and cognitive competence development goals of pupils and students. it became known as a result of bibliographic research on the subject. From this point of view, the fact that a clear functional pedagogical algorithm has not been developed in the scientific field on the issues of logical thinking, pedagogical thinking, at the same time indicates the actual scientific-practical situation of the issue and the need for study.

Drawing up a pedagogical map of the methodical development of logical thinking based on the current situation and actuality, and the two-way development of the logical thinking skills of future elementary school teachers, that is, practical support in the deep formation of the students' worldview by the teachers directly It is a necessary scientific task to create a model that gives and summarizes the competencies of pedagogical professional thinking in a complex state.

It is worth saying that in the process of pedagogical re-training and education organization, creative assimilation of best practices and adaptation to the educational practice of our country is the main object of every branch of science and scientific activity.

Therefore, after acquiring these skills and knowledge, the future primary school teacher will have the ability to think logically, mental development, worldview, communicative literacy and self-esteem of children according to educational standards. It is important to form the capacity for self-awareness, to think freely, to understand the opinions of others, and to express one's own opinion fluently orally and in writing.

Today, the modern requirements for pedagogues are directed towards the development of education, requiring the use of new forms of its organization, which synthesize the elements of cognitive, game, search and educational interaction. Society needs independent thinking, intellectually strong and creative people who make unconventional decisions and are not afraid of it.

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